

**Problematizing Contrastive Linguistics: The Connection Between
Interlanguage and Error Analysis**

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Annotation

This paper challenges contrastive linguistics by highlighting the relationship between interlanguage and error analysis. For data collection and analysis, a quantitative approach was used. To compare and contrast linguistic and socio-cultural data between the shona and the english languages, the researchers used the techniques of contrastive analysis. Although the subject verb agreement between the two languages resembles each other, there are also similarities in that the shona language is implicit in addressing the subject's gender, while the english language is explicit in identifying the subject's gender by the use of explicit pronouns. The findings show that the difficulties in language acquisition are caused by differences between the new language and learners first language. In addition, the two languages studied in this report have distinct typological features. In the study, contrastive analysis methods are suggested for language teaching and learning.

Key words: Contrastive analysis, error analysis, interlanguage, learning problem

Contrastive linguistics, also known as contrastive analysis, is a branch of linguistics that investigates the similarities between two or more languages, rather than their likenesses. The ca hypothesis has three mains: the strong, the weak, and the moderate. In his book languages and logic, which was published in 1941, benjamin lee whorf coined and used the term "contrastive linguistics," which made the distinction between comparative and contrastive linguistics. Ca considers phonology, syntax, and semantics aspects, particularly in order to improve language teaching and translation. This paper will explore contrastive linguistics as a linguistic discipline, focusing on the discipline's historical history and the relationship between interlanguage and error analysis. Findings and discussions contrastive analysis of english and shona languages the purpose of contrastive research is to compare linguistic and socio-cultural data across different languages or within particular

languages in order to establish language-specific, typological, and/or universal patterns, categories, and features. In the same study of practical theory theory, the contrastive analysis hypothesis claims that difficulties in language acquisition arise from the differences between the new language and learners' first language interference. The larger the differences, the easier it is to understand the new language. As a learning tool, the study is of utmost importance.

Contrary linguistics is problematic because it ignores all similarities and differences between two or more languages. Because languages are made up of many different language classes, it is impossible to compare and distinguish them. -the three models (strong, weak, and moderate) are often confused in terms of application, which can result in inconclusive tests and findings. -the difficulty of comparing certain aspects of language such as the temporal, aspectual, and modal systems of verbs, as well as areas such as race, or the functional/semantic values of prepositions; -the central point of contention is the question of equivalence or tertium comparationis; -adequate computerized facilities and equipment to carry out this type of research. Discussion the proponents of error analysis have chastised contrastive analysis for focusing on similarities between L1 and L2 and overlooking variables that may influence the second language learner's success, such as his learning and communication skills, training methods, and overgeneralization. The weaker version of the comparisonist approach is that: linguistic difficulties are explained as posteriori rather than as being predicted as a priori, enabling readers to identify the source of error by utilizing and intuitively contrasting a general knowledge of L1 and L2. In other words, the problems are explained as errors. The development of error analysis was based on a contrast analysis model. Therefore, error analysis was developed by researchers to determine what learners know about L2 by means of analysis and description of learners' mistakes. In the same way, error analysis led to the study of interlanguage as a hypothesis. In the sense that all theories of second language learning are derived from the other, contrast analysis, error analysis, and interlanguage are all related. All theories that aim to improve second language comprehension include contrast, error analysis, and interlanguage. Contrastive analysis was not limited to the learner rather than predicting the shortcomings of the second language learner, as shown by the comparison of L1 and L2. Both approaches helped us to grasp some of the reasons for L2 learners' inaccuracies. Conclusion in the case of contrastive analysis, error analysis, and interlanguage, earlier theories contributed to the development of newer theories. In the new theory, what was lacking in the previous model was included. Contrastive analysis begins with a

comparison of two-language systems and assumes only the areas of difficulty or error for the second language learner, while error analysis begins with mistakes in second language learning and examines them in the wider context of their sources and significance.

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